

addition of both anionic and non-ionic surfactants even at a lower concentration ($\geq 1 \times 10^{-3}\%$) renders the electrode reaction of In(III) totally irreversible. The values of αn_a and $k_{t,n}^0$ have been calculated at the concentrations of ionic and non-ionic surfactants where the electrode reaction of In(III) becomes totally irreversible and thereafter the influence of increasing concentrations of the surfactants on the values of the kinetic parameters has been studied. A perusal of these values shows that both αn_a and $k_{t,n}^0$ decrease with increasing concentrations of the surfactants. It follows from this that the reversible electrode reaction of In(III) in 0.1 M KCl tends towards irreversibility on the addition of ionic and non-ionic surfactants and that the electrode reaction becomes more irreversible with the addition of increasing concentrations of the surfactants. This is further supported by a decrease in i_d and a negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ in the presence of increasing concentrations of the surfactants. The decrease in i_d and a negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ with increasing concentrations of surfactants indicate^{1,2} inhibition of the electrode process of the depolarizers. This may be due to an increase in surface-coverage of the dropping mercury electrode^{1,4}.

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Syntheses of 2-Hydroxyisocarbostyrils

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AS 2-hydroxyisocarbostyrils are effective anti-depressant and powerful tranquiliser¹, a convenient synthesis of this class of compounds is desirable. We reported² earlier the synthesis of 2-hydroxyisocarbostyrils by nitrosation of indan-1-ones and 3-alkyl(aryl)indan-1-ones with butyl nitrite in presence of sodium methoxide. Similar transformations of 2-alkylindan-1-ones have been described by Moriconi and coworkers^{3,4}. Earlier, indeno(3':2'-3:4)isocoumarin was converted into 2-hydroxyindeno(3':2'-3:4)isocarbostyril by the action of hydroxylamine⁵. We now report a synthesis of 2-hydroxyisocarbostyrils by the action of hydroxylamine hydrochloride on 4-acetylisochroman-1,3-dione, isocoumarins and isocoumarincarboxylic acids separately in the presence of pyridine.

2-Hydroxyisocarbostyrils (9 to 13) were obtained by heating isocoumarins (1 to 5), respectively, with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in presence of pyridine. Similar experiments on 3-methylisocoumarin-4-carboxylic acid (6) resulted in the formation of 2-hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin (10) with decarboxylation, which was characterised by the preparation of its acetate and benzoate derivatives (Scheme 1). The pmr spectrum of 10 showed resonances at δ 2.58 (s, 3H, CH₃), 6.55 (broad s, 1H, vinyl), 8.5 (m, 3H, C-8 peri proton), 7.38-7.74 (m, 3H, aromatic) and 10.25 (broad, 1H, NOH exchangeable with D₂O). The ir spectrum of the same compound showed absorptions at 1640 cm⁻¹.

10 was also obtained from similar experiments on 4-acetylisochroman-1,3-dione (8). This transformation obviously involves a rearrangement and decarboxylation, which presumably follows the mechanistic course as in Scheme 2.

While this work was almost complete, we noticed a recent publication of Usgaonkar *et al*⁶ who reported similar conversion of 3-alkyl (Me, Et, Pr)-7-hydroxyisocoumarins and 3-alkyl (Me, Et, Pr)-7-hydroxyisocoumarin-4-carboxylic acids with hydroxylamine in presence of aqueous sodium carbonate. It is interesting to note that they obtained 3-alkyl (Me, Et, Pr)-2,7-dihydroxy-4-carboxyisocarbostyrils from the 4-acyl (MeCO, EtCO, PrCO)-7-hydroxyisochroman-1,3-diones while in our case we isolated the decarboxylated products from analogous experiments. The mechanism proposed by them (attack of hydroxylamine on acyl carbonyl group) does not seem to be tenable under the experimental conditions adopted by us.

1. $R_1=R_2=R_3=R_4=H$
2. $R_1=R_2=R_3=H, R_4=CH_3$
3. $R_1=R_2=H, R_3=R_4=CH_3$
4. $R_1=R_2=R_3=H, R_4=COOH$
5. $R_1=R_2=OCH_3, R_3=H, R_4=COOH$
6. $R_1=R_2=H, R_3=COOH, R_4=CH_3$
7. $R_1=R_2=R_4=H, R_3=COOH$
9. $R_1=R_2=R_3=R_4=H$
10. $R_1=R_2=R_3=H, R_4=OH$
11. $R_1=R_2=H, R_3=R_4=CH_3$
12. $R_1=R_2=R_3=H, R_4=COOH$
13. $R_1=R_2=OCH_3, R_3=H, R_4=COOH$

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

The reaction of isocoumarin-4-carboxylic acid (7) with hydroxylamine gave a different result. A compound, m.p. 258-59°, was obtained as the sole product which gave magenta ferric reaction and

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showed ir absorption at 1635 cm^{-1} . On the basis of the presence of pmr signals at δ 2.51, 3.42 (OH, exchangeable with D_2O), 3.84 and 10.5 (NOH, exchangeable with D_2O) in the integral ratio of 1 : 1 : 2 : 1, elemental analysis (molecular composition $C_9H_9O_3N$) and ir data, we tentatively suggest the carbinol structure (14) for the compound.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, model 577. The pmr spectra were recorded on Varian A-60.

2-Hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin (10) :

Method A. From 3-methylisocoumarin (2) : A solution of 2 (500 mg) in pyridine (1 ml) was heated with hydroxylamine hydrochloride on a boiling water bath for 2 hr. The mixture was then cooled and cold hydrochloric acid (30 ml; 2 N) was added to it whereby compound (10) separated as solid which was filtered, washed with cold water, dilute hydrochloric acid and water, respectively,

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*
9, 11, 12 AND 13

Starting compound	Product	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	IR values (cm^{-1})
1 ^a	9	186-87 (reported ^{1,2} 184-85.5)	70	1630
3 ^a	11	204-205	60	1630
4 ^a	12	227-28	70	1690
5 ^{1,1}	13	215-16	65	1620 1685 1610

* All the compounds gave satisfactory analysis for carbon and hydrogen.

and crystallised from acetone as white plates (350 mg), m.p. 172-73° (lit.³ m.p. 172.5-73°); (Found : C, 68.4; H, 5.4. $C_{10}H_9O_3N$ requires C, 68.6; H, 5.2%). IR (KBr) : 1640 cm^{-1} (lactam carbonyl); pmr ($CDCl_3$) : δ 2.58 (s, 3H, CH_3), 6.55 (slightly broad s, 1H, vinyl), 7.38-7.74 (m, 3H aromatic), 8.5 (m, 1H, C-8 peri aromatic proton) and 10.25 (broad s, 1H, NOH, exchangeable with D_2O).

The acetate derivative crystallised from benzene in colourless needles, m.p. 128-29° (Found : C, 66.2; H, 5.3. $C_{12}H_{11}O_5N$ requires C, 66.4; H, 5.1%). IR (KBr) : 1780 (ester carbonyl) and 1660 cm^{-1} (lactam carbonyl).

The benzoate derivative crystallised from benzene as colourless needles, m.p. 168° (lit.³ m.p. 167-68°) (Found : C, 72.9; H, 4.8. $C_{17}H_{13}O_5N$ requires C, 73.1; H, 4.7%).

Compounds (9) and (11 to 13) were prepared in an analogous manner from the related isocoumarins (1) and (3 to 5), respectively.

